

MULTICULTURAL ASPECTS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' DISCOURSE (WRITTEN) COMPETENCIES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6881552>

Abstract. *This paper discusses multicultural aspects of improving students' discourse (written) competencies (on the example of the english language) students' professional writing competence, types of competencies, and explains the importance of improving professional writing competence in English lessons. The effective ways of improving students' professional writing competence are shown in the article.*

Keywords: *competence, writing, professional, development, standard, education, approach, communicative, intellectual, linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, adapt.*

МУЛЬТИКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ДИСКУРСИВНЫХ (ПИСЬМЕННЫХ) КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА)

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются поликультурные аспекты совершенствования у студентов дискурсивных (письменных) компетенций (на примере английского языка), профессиональной письменной компетенции студентов, виды компетенций, а также объясняется важность совершенствования профессиональной письменной компетенции на уроках английского языка. В статье показаны эффективные пути совершенствования профессиональной письменной компетенции студентов.*

Ключевые слова: *компетентность, письмо, профессионал, развитие, стандарт, образование, подход, коммуникативный, интеллектуальный, лингвистический, социолингвистический, прагматический, адаптирующий.*

INTRODUCTION

To the trends of modern development of the field of education in our republic a lot of experience has been accumulated in adaptation, development of innovative teaching technologies. Modern information and writing to the educational process technologies, foreign experiences are being applied. Teaching humanities ensuring continuity and consistency, creating a modern methodology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Competency approach to state educational standards in the humanities on the basis of improvement, developing a new generation of educational-methodical complexes Uzbekistan on October 19, 2020 for the purpose of exit and implementation "State education of higher education" of the Minister of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic standard. Classification of higher education directions and specialties" Uzbekistan Order No. 11 on the approval of the state standard of the Republic was adopted. This command is an important factor in the further development of the educational process it has been. Professional writing competence of students in English language classes in higher education organization for the purpose of improvement and acquired knowledge of students the ability to use in practice leads to improvement of skills. Education integrated with innovative technologies to effectively organize the process, use on an integrative basis is today's demand.

RESULTS

Nowadays, in order to become an expert in foreign languages, especially it is necessary to improve professional writing competence in English. Therefore, high great attention is paid to students' professional discourse (written) competence in the educational process being directed. In the methodical training system of a foreign language teacher, it is necessary to adequately prepare this specialist, to teach him a special form of culture, a language that is a medium of thinking and is carried out by a person, the country of the language being studied, the principles, methods and tools of teaching this language. It is important to educate about each of these components is accompanied by certain theoretical knowledge that underpins and regulates a certain variety of professional activities. Sufficient professional qualifications and professional culture are a necessary condition for the implementation of pedagogical activities. The student maximizes the language to improve professional discourse (written) competence level, able to speak and write competently about the language, appropriate psychological and pedagogical and should have methodological knowledge and general cultural training. So, the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language is determined by many factors, the most important of them is the teacher's communication with students in class is able to use the language being taught. Communicative and educational function the speech of the teacher plays a very important role in its implementation. Students are each other if he has a communicative culture to the extent that he interacts with their skill is shown. However, practice shows that the writing activity of students in class is still a weak point, which leads to difficulties in solving academic writing problems. Apparently, this is the result of insufficient preparation in oral communication.

DISCUSSION

Students' writing is rightfully one of the most effective tools in the educational process is considered. A student's skill, especially in foreign language classes, is direct word knowledge depends on the level. It's about diction and words, expressing one's thoughts clearly and theirs requires constant and purposeful work on reasonable proof of its correctness. All of the above is related to students' discourse (written) skills in class purposefully determines what role to play in teaching. It can be seen that the writing and pedagogical activity of a foreign language teacher filled with its own content. How to teach academic writing professionally to students, the main point is to allow students to control the learning process providing material that can be used in teaching discourse (written) competence, is the selection of speech units.

CONCLUSIONS

The basis of English language education is based on students' professional discourse (written) competence by students in the educational process, the essence of which is organized in English acquired knowledge, skills and competences during personal life, as well as to improve the competencies to be used in professional and social activities referral is considered. In the competence approach, the teaching goals are self-awareness by students, ways to achieve learning goals in the educational process understanding, increasing the learning activity of students, students as individual's adaptation to society and independent life through self-development, it is necessary to consider priority directions such as socialization.

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